

ORGANIZING STUDENTS' EDUCATIONAL AND RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17277679>

During the teaching process, the interaction between the teacher and student is typically established through the exchange of information. The core information is usually presented by the teacher in a thematic structure. Therefore, in preparing physics teachers, it is essential not only to provide theoretical knowledge but also to train young professionals who are capable of conducting experiments and practical demonstrations. This is especially important as modern students, who are well-versed in information technologies, may not fully engage with physics if it is taught only through theory.

As a result, today's physics teachers must select topic-appropriate educational research activities and demonstrate relevant experiments during lessons, providing scientific explanations of physical processes.

For example, to explain the radiation process of bodies, hot and cold objects are used to illustrate how radiation intensity depends on temperature. An experiment is set up using a calorimeter, thermometer, and spirit lamp. First, a cold object is placed in the calorimeter with water, and the equilibrium temperature is measured. Then the object is heated with a spirit lamp until it reaches a certain temperature, after which the lamp is turned off and the new temperature is measured. The amount of heat absorbed is calculated using a formula. The heat gained by the object during heating is subsequently radiated during cooling. This experiment provides a scientific basis for exploring heat insulation systems for buildings in winter and for developing materials with high heat retention. In modern construction, materials with such properties are increasingly used to save and retain heat.

In higher education institutions, the organization of educational research is particularly important in teaching atomic physics. Atomic physics, which bridges classical and quantum physics, explains the structure of atoms and how larger systems such as molecules, matter, and objects are formed. Research on the micro-world is often presented visually using information technology tools.

For instance, in a lab session to determine Planck's constant, students conduct an experiment using the photoelectric effect. They separate white light

into spectral components using a glass prism, direct one monochromatic light beam onto a photoelement, measure the resulting photocurrent voltage, and then use the law of conservation of energy to calculate the numerical value of Planck's constant using the appropriate formula.

Conclusion

Educational research enables students to gain a deep understanding of physical processes, reinforces theoretical explanations, and ultimately increases the effectiveness of the learning process.

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